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The Ecology Issue

YUAN LIN
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2024

THE ECOLOGY ISSUE

COVER IMAGE
WEEDsilence

by Hiu-Yan Wong, Ho-Lam
Wang, & Benni Pong

YUAN LIN
2024

THE ECOLOGY
ISSUE

Editorial: Biodiversity, climate change, and resilience

In recent years, the defining role of landscape architecture among the built environment disciplines tends to lie in its unique contributions in tackling issues of biodiversity, climate change, and resilience. The Hong Kong Institute of Landscape Architects (HKILA) have been instrumental in positioning ourselves locally and internationally in taking upon the challenges posed by this re-orientation of the discipline. Significantly, the HKILA have over the past years organised and co-organised events including the *Resilient City: Landscape Planning Towards Climate Adaptation Conference* in 2019, the *Northern Metropolis: Hong Kong/Shenzhen Ecological and Environmental Symposium* in 2023, the *Hong Kong 2024 International Urban Forestry Conference* themed 'Green Metropolis: The Crucial Role of Urban Forests for a Sustainable Future' in 2024, and the upcoming *International Climate and Biodiversity Conference: Nature-based Solutions (Nbs) in Action* that is planned to take place in March 2025. Some of these events are recorded in the Events section of this issue.

HKILA President Paul Chan currently chairs the International Federation of Landscape Architects, Asia-Pacific Region's (IFLA-APR) Climate Change and Biodiversity Working Group and have in the past year represented HKILA and IFLA in important international events such as the *2024 United Nations Biodiversity Conference (CBD COP16)* in Colombia, the *NBS X* event in Malaysia, and the *2025 Nature-based Solutions for Climate Conference* hosted by the Nature Conservancy

and Civic Exchange in Hong Kong. Some of this work is covered by Paul's article on mainstreaming Nature-based Solutions. The articles contributed by Snøhetta and Arup also showcases how some of these concerns are carried out in practice.

The special position played by landscape architects lies in their natural affinity and intimate relationship with land, soil, plants, and ecology. These intricate relationships are narrated from multidimensional perspectives through the contributions of Howie Kong and Vicki Liu's articles on bioactive soil and rubber landscapes. The nativity of plants is a crucial topic in this discussion and is visited by the articles of Ting Wang and Mathew Pryor. The issue of urban heat in relation to green infrastructure and urban landscape is explored by Yilun Li, Chao Ren, Zheng, Wanlu Ouyang, and Lilian Tsang. Finally, from a historical perspective, Carol Ma reviews the trajectory of urban tree management in Hong Kong and discusses our way forward.

Following the publication of this issue of *Yuan Lin* under the theme of 'Ecology', we look forward to continuing this discussion through different challenges and platforms including the IFLA World Congress and APR Congress, which the HKILA will host in 2026 with the working theme of 'Watersheds and Coastlines'. Along these lines, HKILA is also strengthening our interdisciplinary collaborations with multiple partners and these initiatives will be reported in our social media accounts and the upcoming issues of *Yuan Lin*.

Yin-Lun Chan
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Invasive or Native?

A Landscape Design Experiment in Shenzhen

Ting Wang

ABSTRACT: In the face of global climate change, ecological disasters are unfolding one after another. Ecology has evolved from a scientific study of organisms' relationships with their environments to a widely discussed public issue. The concerns have shifted from controlling nature to embracing ecological restoration and harmonious coexistence, including advocating for rewilding to restore spaces to their natural states. These shifts prompt reflection on the human-nature relationship. How can landscape design, a field blending science and art, engage with ecology? This paper examines the recent debate in China over the Memorial Park of the 19th International Botanical Congress in Shenzhen, which proposed a 'plant-free' approach. This paper explores what would happen to the ecology of a piece of land if nothing were planted? What challenges does such an experimental approach present? How do experts from various disciplines perceive ecology and nature differently?

Multifaceted Relationship Between Landscape and Ecology

Ecological considerations in landscape design have been common practice for decades. Since the 1960s, Ian McHarg emphasized the importance of scientific understanding of site ecology informing landscape design and planning in his book *Design with Nature* (McHarg, 1969). Artists have also used land art to address environmental issues, intertwining landscape design with ecology. For instance,

in the 1970s, Robert Smithson created the "Spiral Jetty," a large-scale earthwork sculpture winding counterclockwise into the water. The natural tides' impact on landscape works draws attention to unique environmental challenges such as water scarcity, land use changes, and pollution in the Great Salt Lake, US (Smithson, 1972; Rubio, 2012). Given that landscape design blends science and art, what is our role in addressing ecological issues within landscape architecture?

Fig 1. Location Map of the IBC Memorial Park and Landscape Design Site with Border Contexts (Made by author)

The Memorial Park for the 19th International Botanical Congress (IBC) is a contemporary landscape design project in China that integrates both ecological science and land art. Located at the confluence of the Xinzhou and Shenzhen Rivers, near the Guangdong Neilingding Futian Mangrove National Nature Reserve, the Mai Po Inner Deep Bay Ramsar Site, and Shenzhen's urban area, the park serves as a transitional zone between urban environments and natural habitats, such as mangroves (5.7 ha) and tidal flats (3.9 ha). Originally a landfill site with poor soil quality, the area was transformed in 2019 by Guangzhou Turenscape's landscape architects into a garden to commemorate the 2017 IBC and promote botanical science. The park was completed in 2020.

Rethinking the Concept of 'Memorial' for Plants

Memorial gardens hold significant cultural value, providing spaces for remembrance and reflection. Traditionally, memorial designs incorporate symbolic plants, axial lines, and iconic features like monuments, towers, fountains, and pavilions. Notable examples include Maya Lin's Vietnam Veterans Memorial Garden and the Diana, Princess of Wales Memorial Garden (Francis, Neophytou, & Kellaher, 2020; Sully, 2010). Memorial forests, often

within cemeteries, allow individuals to honor loved ones by planting trees. The Remembrance Forest at the National Memorial Arboretum in the UK exemplifies this approach, offering a meaningful space for tree planting. China has similar memorial forests, such as Nanjing Yuhuatai Martyrs' Cemetery, the Shenyang Korean War Martyrs' Cemetery, and the Peace Cemetery. Public participation on memorial days allows citizens to honor history through tree planting.

However, designers of the Memorial Park for the 19th IBC sought to challenge traditional memorial garden approaches by proposing a radical concept: not planting a single tree but allowing natural succession to restore a forest, thus commemorating the intrinsic power of plant life (Turenscape, 2024). The lead landscape designer, inspired by ecologist Aldo Leopold's "land ethic" (Leopold, 2003), argues that humans should extend their ethics to include the land—soil, water, plants, and animals—which are often overlooked but are essential to ecosystem functioning. This non-anthropocentric approach critiques the longstanding preference for ornamental plants in Chinese public parks.

Common methods used in forest restoration within traditional landscape design

involved the use of fast-growing, cold-tolerant tree species to establish economic or landscape forests quickly. In the discussions surrounding this project design, alternative approaches have been proposed, such as the Miyawaki Method suggested by the team's plant designer. Originating from the renowned Japanese vegetation ecologist Dr. Akira Miyawaki, this method is based on the New Succession Theory and aims to restore vegetation using native tree species to re-establish quasi-natural forests closely resembling the local natural environment (Wang et al., 2002). By transforming soil, controlling moisture conditions, and nurturing seedlings of native tree species, the Miyawaki method can establish top-tier community types adapted to local climates in a relatively short period (20-50 years). In contrast, natural succession typically takes centuries, if not millennia, starting from barren or treeless land and gradually evolving into a forest ecosystem.

Considering the unique geographical

advantage of this project located in the HK-SZ border exclusion zone, where access is limited to the general public and human disturbances are minimal, landscape designers saw this as a rare opportunity to experiment with natural succession and thus decided to adopt this more radical design concept. It is important to note that while natural succession serves as the guiding principle, this does not imply complete inaction, as the site's poor soil quality necessitates soil replacement initially. Embracing the concept of a soil seed bank, the designers aimed to introduce natural soil from the natural areas of Shenzhen to allow seeds within the soil to germinate spontaneously. They also designed a low-impact observation trail as a fundamental facility for future environmental education.

The concept of a Soil Seed Bank posits that unlike typical horticultural planting soil, natural topsoil often harbors a multitude of seeds. Here, seeds encompass a

Fig 2. Observation path in the memorial park, made of stainless steel and weathering steel (Taken by author in 2023 summer)

Fig 3. Source location of the introduced soil in the park (Taken by author)

Fig 4. Original view of the site before design (Source: Guangzhou Turenscape)

broad definition, representing any reproductive life form that can propagate, including seeds of flowering plants, spores, rhizomes, collectively referred to as the seed sources within the soil. Additionally, the movement and dispersal of seeds by wind, birds, and insects contribute to introducing new seeds to the site.

Challenges of ‘Design Nothing’?

During the project design process, experts held differing views on ecology. Aquatic ecology specialists expressed concerns that without intervention in plant growth, the site could become a source of invasive plants. Conversely, garden making experts supported the experiment, believing that small size of the site would make invasive species manageable.

One major challenge was collecting natural soil. Initially, the team planned to gather topsoil from over 20 natural reserves in Shenzhen, but this proved difficult due to environmental protection laws prohibiting soil extraction in natural and protected areas as natural topsoil is a precious resource. Consequently, adjustments had to be made during the construction phase. The team identified plots within parks or natural reserves slated for development, where they salvaged the topsoil during construction. Ultimately, soil was sourced from four locations in Shenzhen, including parks and nurseries. Due to insufficient quantities, the topsoil layer across the entire site varied in thickness from 10 to 20 centimeters.

Fig 5. Monitoring cameras show the percentage of plants coverage in eight 2mx2m survey quadrats (Made by author, source: The 19th International Botanical Congress Memorial Garden“Project 2121”2020-2021 Report)

Following the park's opening, managing invasive plants became a key issue. Prior to the design, the original site was dominated by herbaceous communities, observing 18 plant species, including 6 invasive species and 9 native plants. In the first year after completion from 2019 to 2020, no dominant community had emerged, with mainly slow-growing grasses from the Poaceae family prevailing. Invasive species such as mimosa were present but remained stunted. After the second year and a rainy season, reeds began to grow rapidly, accompanied by the appearance of some woody species. A total of 79 plant species were identified based on the 2020-2021 plant survey. Among them, 17 species were classified as invasive (Figure 4), including devil's needles, German chamomile, and silver wattle. During my visit in the summer of 2023, the ground cover of invasive plants had become dominant, but many native woody plants had also begun to grow tall, such as paper mulberry (*Broussonetia papyrifera*) and chinaberry.

Addressing these invasive plants has become a strategic game between humans and nature. The ecological management of invasive plants typically requires significant human and financial investment. Currently, the management entity of the memorial park, the Shenzhen Mangrove Conservation Foundation, has planted rows of *Pittosporum tobira* in the transitional zone between the terrestrial and

maritime mangrove areas. This physical barrier aims to isolate ground-level invasive plants and minimize their impact on the Shenzhen River and the Deep Bay. Through technological monitoring, real-time biodiversity data and natural changes are being collected. The park is equipped with 8 cameras monitoring 8 plant sample plots and 18 infrared cameras monitoring wildlife (MCF, 2021).

Additionally, the MCF, in collaboration with the Shenzhen municipal government, has launched the "2121 Century Plan - Natural Science Experiment Program," aiming to open the memorial park to the public, especially botanical research institutions, plant enthusiasts, and youth. This initiative encourages individuals to document the plant succession on this land and actively engage the public in ecological maintenance at the park. From October 2020 to September 2021, the park hosted 58 "Green Monster" events, engaging 1469 participants in environmental education. Collectively, they cleared 3260.5 kg of invasive species, including *Bidens pilosa* (64%), *Tephrosia purpurea* (23%), *Mimosa diplotricha* (9%), *Leucaena leucocephala* (2%), and *Desmodium totuosum* (2%).

The Fluidity of Native and Invasive Species Concepts in Ecology

The term "invasive species" was originally defined and popularized by Charles Elton, a British ecologist, in his 1958 book "The Ecology of Invasions by Animals

Fig 7. Explanation sign set up next to the invasive plants and an introduction to the “Fight Green Monster” nature education events. (taken by author)

and Plants.” In common understanding, invasive species are non-native organisms that, upon introduction to a new environment, can negatively impact the local ecosystem, economy, or human health. Applied ecologists often advocate for the immediate removal of invasive species, believing that the unpredictability arises from the introduction of a single species that can disrupt the entire food chain within a site, making it difficult to predict and manage.

Conversely, plant philosopher Michael Marder argues against the removal of invasive plants, suggesting that as ecosystems mature, new predators will naturally emerge to control existing invasive species, thus achieving a relative balance within the ecosystem (Marder, 2013). The landscape designers of this project adopt a more open-ended approach, akin to romantic artists, viewing the project not just as an ecological endeavor but also as a land art project with profound sociological implications surpassing ecological significance. The emergence of invasive plants may serve as a warning to urban dwellers about the crisis of invasive species in urbanized soils and the impending global shortage of healthy soil in the near future.

In fact, the distinction between native and non-native species in ecology is a relative, subject to change. For instance, reeds are considered invasive species in the United States but are native species in China. In contrast, *Solidago decurrens*, which China defines as an invasive species, is a native species in the United States. Therefore, the significance of this experimental project lies in providing an opportunity to observe the relationship between landscape and temporality. What will this site look like in 100 years or even further into the future? In future ecological monitoring, it is crucial to explore when and how an identified invasive species transitions into a native species. This transformation, known as “Naturalization,” signifies that introduced species have integrated harmoniously into the larger ecology, no longer causing disruption.

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Fig 6. A row of *Pittosporum tobira* planted between the plant succession area and the mangrove restoration area in the memorial park (Taken by author)

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Appendix: Species List

No.	Family	Chinese Name	Latin Name	National Alien Invasive species list Grades
1	禾本科	白茅	<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	
2	Poaceae	地毯草	<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	
3		狗牙根	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	
4		畫眉草	<i>Eragrostis pilosa</i>	
5		星星草	<i>Puccinellia tenuiflora</i>	
6		結縷草	<i>Zoysia japonica</i>	
7		類蘆	<i>Neyraudia reynaudiana</i>	
8		蘆葦	<i>Phragmites australis</i>	
9		蘆竹	<i>Arundo donax</i>	
10		五節芒	<i>Miscanthus foridulus</i>	
11		兩耳草	<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	
12		圓果雀稗	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> var. <i>orbiculare</i>	
13		糠稷	<i>Panicum bisulcatum</i>	
14		糖蜜草	<i>Melinis minutiflora</i>	
15		紅毛草	<i>Melinis repens</i>	Third (Moderate)
16	莎草科	異型莎草	<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	
17	Cyperaceae	碎米莎草	<i>Cyperus iria</i>	
18		斷節莎	<i>Cyperus odoratus</i>	
19	西番蓮科 Passifloraceae	七龍珠果	<i>Passiflora foetida</i>	Third (Moderate)
20	大戟科	飛揚草	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	
21	Euphorbiaceae	通奶草	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i>	
22		血桐	<i>Macaranga tanarius</i>	
23		葉下珠	<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i>	
24	馬鞭草科 Verbenaceae	馬纓丹	<i>Lantana camara</i>	First (Massive)
25	茄科 Solanaceae	水茄	<i>Solanum torvum</i>	
26	旋花科 Convolvulaceae	五爪金龍	<i>Ipomoea cairica</i>	First (Massive)
27		三裂葉薯	<i>Ipomoea triloba</i>	
28		野地菟絲子	<i>Cuscuta campestris</i>	
29		菟絲子	<i>Cuscuta chinensis</i>	
30		籬欄網	<i>Merremia hederacea</i>	
31		牽牛	<i>Ipomoea nil</i>	Second
32	錦葵科	地桃花	<i>Urena lobata</i>	
33	Malvaceae	拔毒散	<i>Sida szechuensis</i>	
34		美麗異木棉	<i>Ceiba speciosa</i>	
35	菊科 Asteraceae	鬼針草	<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	First (Massive)
36		微甘菊	<i>Mikania micrantha</i>	First (Massive)
37		鵝腸	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>	
38		南美洲追窮 其菊	<i>Sphagneticola trilobata</i>	Second
39		鵝不食草	<i>Epalles australis</i>	
40		夜香牛	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i>	
41		羽芒菊	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	
42		藿香薊	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	First Grade
43	茜草科	耳草	<i>Hedyotis auricularia</i>	
44	Rubiaceae	雞矢藤	<i>Paederia foetida</i>	
45		闊葉豐花草	<i>Spermacoce alata</i>	First (Massive)
46		光葉豐花草	<i>Spermiacoce remota</i>	
47	豆科	三裂葉野葛	<i>Pueraria phaseoloides</i>	
48	Fabaceae	光莢含羞草	<i>Mimosa bimucronata</i>	First (Massive)
49		巴西含羞草	<i>Mimosa diplotricha</i>	
50		含羞草	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Second
51		葫蘆茶	<i>Tadehagi triquetrum</i>	
52		海南黃檀	<i>Dalbergia hainanensis</i>	
53		灰毛豆	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	
54		翅莢決明	<i>Senna alata</i>	
55		鏈莢豆	<i>Alysicarpus vaginalis</i>	
56		南洋楹	<i>Falcataria moluccana</i>	
57		假地豆	<i>Desmodium heterocarpon</i>	
58		南美洲山蝗	<i>Desmodium tortuosum</i>	
59		田菁	<i>Sesbania cannabina</i>	Second
60		大葉相思	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i>	
61		台灣相思	<i>Acacia confusa</i>	
62		馬佔相思	<i>Acacia mangium</i>	
63		銀合歡	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Second
64		豬屎豆	<i>Crotalaria pallida</i>	
65	虎耳草科 Saxifragaceae	槭葉草	<i>Mukdenia rossii</i>	
66	桃金娘科	烏墨	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	
67	Myrtaceae	蒲桃	<i>Syzygium jambos</i>	
68		洋蒲桃	<i>Syzygium samarangense</i>	
69	桑科	構樹	<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i>	
70	Moraceae	垂葉榕	<i>Ficus benjamina</i>	
71		綠黃葛樹	<i>Ficus virens</i>	
72	榆科 Ulmaceae	山黃麻	<i>Trema tomentosa</i>	
73	楝科 Meliaceae	楝	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	
74	遠志科 Polygalaceae	小扁豆	<i>Polygala tatarinowii</i>	
75	莧科	喜旱蓮子草	<i>Aleranthera philoxeroides</i>	First (Massive)
76	Amaranthaceae	刺莧	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	First (Massive)
77		青葙	<i>Celosia argentea</i>	Second
78	羅漢松科 Podocarpaceae	羅漢松	<i>Podocarpus macrophyllus</i>	
79	海金沙科 Lygodiaceae	海金沙	<i>Lygodium japonicum</i>	

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